

GREEN ECONOMY ORGANIZATION IN ENSURING SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract. The article highlights the specific features of green economy digitization as a key factor in economic development, and digitalization and green economy are presented as the most important factors of sustainable development. Digitization is presented as an innovation in the use of natural resources and improving the quality of nature use in sustainable development.

Keywords: Green economy, Paris Climate Agreement, Greening, digital technologies, alternative energy sources, sustainable development.

In the modern world, the topic of green economy is one of the most relevant topics in the past few years. One of the main tasks of the transition to a "green" economy is to increase the energy efficiency of the economy and rational use of natural resources. This is achieved through the modernization of technologies and the development of financial mechanisms. In 2018, the Republic of Uzbekistan ratified the Paris Agreement on Climate Change (Paris, December 12, 2015) and undertook a quantitative commitment to reduce greenhouse gas emissions per unit of GDP by 10% by 2030 compared to 2010 levels.

In the framework of fulfilling the obligations of the Paris Agreement, the country's medium-term priority areas for reducing greenhouse gas emissions are being implemented through a number of strategic and sectoral plans, programs, as well as regulatory and legal documents, which include reducing energy and resource consumption in the economy, widely introducing energy-saving technologies into production, expanding the use of renewable energy sources, and eliminating the consequences of the ecological crisis in the Aral Sea.

Thus, according to a study on the state of the environment and pollution in the world, almost all natural resources are subject to serious anthropogenic pressure. Such ecological economic problems require the greening of the economy.

One of the main ways to “green” the economy is innovation and the introduction of new technologies into various areas of activity. In 2020, after the rapid transition of many companies to the digitalization system, a phase of radical restructuring of the economy began. Thus, the digital economy is a new economic activity based on digital technologies, associated with e-business, e-commerce, and the production of digital goods and services. The positive aspects of the use of digital technologies in the green economy are:

- **Increase in labor productivity due to reduced production costs;**
- **Creation of new green jobs, as well as the development of freelance work;**
- **Creation of opportunities for companies to increase their competitiveness, as well as expand the possibilities for the production of environmentally friendly products;**
- **Eliminating poverty and social inequality.**

Thus, the digital economy is essentially a digital economy, leading to the creation of sustainable development technologies. At the beginning of the 21st century, the United Nations put forward 17 global goals that are interconnected priority areas of human development. According to a study conducted by the Global Recovery Observatory of the University of Oxford, supported by the United Nations Environment Program (UNEP), less than 20% of total recovery costs are allocated to environmental problems. The Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-436 dated December 2, 2023 “On measures to increase the effectiveness of reforms aimed at the transition of the Republic of Uzbekistan to a “green” economy by 2030” was adopted. Thus, the digital economy is essentially a digital economy, and the application of digital technologies to a green economy leads to the creation of sustainable development technologies. At the beginning of the 21st century, the United Nations put forward 17 global goals that are interconnected priority areas of human development. According to a study by the Global Recovery Observatory of the University of Oxford, supported by the United Nations Environment Programm (UNEP), less than 20% of total recovery spending is allocated to environmental issues. The Ministry of Economic Development and Poverty Reduction of the Republic of Uzbekistan has been designated as the authorized body for promoting a "green" economy and implementing the principles of "green" growth, coordinating activities to reduce greenhouse gas emissions in economic sectors. Currently, global business is directing a large amount of resources to the development of technologies aimed at preventing climate change and reducing environmental pollution. Alternative energy sources are renewable energy sources obtained through the use of hydropower, wind power, solar power, geothermal energy, biomass and tidal energy. These energy sources, unlike fossil fuels such as oil, natural gas, coal and uranium ore, are inexhaustible, therefore they are called

renewable sources. In recent years, the total capacity of energy production facilities in Uzbekistan has been growing, but the pace of development is much lower than in neighboring countries, especially Russia. Uzbekistan is one of the most vulnerable countries to climate change, since 80% of the country's territory is occupied by grasslands and deserts, so climate change can have a significant impact on the economy of Uzbekistan. Since the early 1950s, the average temperature in the country has increased twice as much as the rate of global warming. Current projections show that, without the necessary mitigation measures, the country's average temperature will rise by 1.8°-3.3° C by 2050. Without additional adaptation measures, the country will face increasing water scarcity and desertification by the middle of this century.

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